

Symmetric closed-form polar factor for the contrast subspace and a polar decomposition derivation of Helmert matrices

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Abstract

Orthogonal parametrisations of the subspace orthogonal to the all-ones vector play an important role in multivariate analysis, compositional data, and linearly constrained models. This paper revisits such parametrisations through polar decomposition and introduces a symmetric, closed-form alternative to classical Helmert matrices. For each dimension, a simple arrowhead matrix is shown to have an orthogonal polar factor that is symmetric, has its first column proportional to the all-ones vector, and whose remaining columns form an explicit orthonormal basis of the contrast subspace. This basis is order-free and arises uniquely as the polar factor of a fixed symmetric operator, yielding an intrinsic orthogonal representation that is invariant under permutations of the coordinates. Within the same framework, a structured triangular matrix is constructed whose orthogonal polar factor coincides with the classical Helmert matrix. This provides an analytic derivation in arbitrary dimension and shows that Helmert contrasts can be characterised as solutions of an associated orthogonal Procrustes problem, rather than as the outcome of a Gram–Schmidt procedure. The analysis clarifies how symmetric and triangular generators lead, respectively, to intrinsic and hierarchical orthonormal bases of the same contrast subspace, and illustrates the structural consequences of these choices through explicit examples.

Keywords: polar decomposition; orthogonal contrasts; Helmert matrices; Householder reflections; rank-one updates; orthogonal Procrustes problems

MSC: 15A23, 15A18

1. Introduction

Orthogonal decompositions associated with linear constraints play a fundamental role in many areas of mathematics and its applications. A particularly simple and recurrent situation arises when vectors are required to be orthogonal to the all-ones vector, leading to the contrast subspace

$$\mathbf{1}^\perp = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n: \mathbf{1}^\top x = 0\}.$$

Several constructions of orthonormal bases for this subspace have been proposed, with the so-called Helmert matrices occupying a prominent position in statistics, econometrics and compositional data analysis.

Historically, Helmert's original work on the probability of observational errors introduced systematic linear combinations of corrections around an arithmetic mean, together with associated error formulas; these combinations already exhibit the hierarchical contrast structure that later underlies the Helmert transformation [1], although no explicit contrast matrix is written down in modern form. Lancaster subsequently formalised and popularised the matrix viewpoint, and the term "Helmert matrices" became standard to denote orthogonal matrices with a prescribed first row (or column) and a triangular pattern of zeros above the diagonal [2]. Different but equivalent conventions exist in the literature regarding the orientation of this triangular structure; the present work adopts the transposed convention, which is immaterial from a geometric or statistical point of view. In what follows we adopt Lancaster's terminology and refer to such orthogonal contrast matrices as Helmert matrices, while keeping Helmert's original paper as the historical source of the underlying system of contrasts.

In most classical treatments, Helmert matrices are obtained via sequential orthogonalisation procedures, typically based on Gram–Schmidt applied to specially prepared generating matrices [3]. This approach leads to the characteristic triangular structure that reflects a prescribed ordering of the coordinates and produces a hierarchical organisation of contrasts within $\mathbf{1}^\perp$. From a structural point of view, the resulting orthonormal basis is therefore not uniquely determined by the subspace itself, but by the algorithmic path and the chosen ordering. This raises the question of whether alternative orthogonal parametrisations of $\mathbf{1}^\perp$ can be obtained by intrinsic matrix-analytic principles, without recourse to sequential procedures or order-dependent constructions. The focus of this work is therefore conceptual and structural rather than computational: the aim is to characterise orthogonal parametrisations of the contrast subspace through intrinsic matrix-analytic principles, without addressing numerical efficiency or algorithmic optimisation.

Let $K \geq 1$. The Helmert matrix $\mathbf{H}_{K+1} \in \mathbb{R}^{(K+1) \times (K+1)}$ is the orthogonal matrix whose first column is proportional to the all-ones vector: $e_1 = \mathbf{1}_K / \sqrt{K+1}$, and whose remaining K columns form an orthonormal basis of $\mathbf{1}^\perp$. These columns, known as Helmert contrasts, are defined recursively: for $j = 2, \dots, K+1$, the j -th column has its first $j-1$ entries equal to $1/\sqrt{j(j-1)}$, its j -th entry equal to $-(j-1)/\sqrt{j(j-1)}$, and zeros elsewhere. Equivalently, the matrix can be written explicitly as

$$\mathbf{H}_{K+1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 & \cdots & 1 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} & \cdots & \frac{1}{\sqrt{(j-1)j}} & \cdots & \frac{1}{\sqrt{K(K+1)}} \\ 1 & -1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 & \cdots & 1 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} & \cdots & \frac{1}{\sqrt{(j-1)j}} & \cdots & \frac{1}{\sqrt{K(K+1)}} \\ 1 & 0 & -2 & \cdots & 1 & \cdots & 1 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} & 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} & \cdots & \frac{1}{\sqrt{(j-1)j}} & \cdots & \frac{1}{\sqrt{K(K+1)}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{(j-1)j}} & \cdots & 1 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} & 0 & 0 & \cdots & \frac{1}{\sqrt{(j-1)j}} & \cdots & \frac{1}{\sqrt{K(K+1)}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & \cdots & -K \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & \cdots & \frac{1}{\sqrt{K(K+1)}} \end{bmatrix}$$

This definition corresponds to a transposed convention of the Helmert matrix with respect to some presentations in the literature; both forms are equivalent and differ only by transposition. The explicit form above makes clear the triangular structure of Helmert contrasts and illustrates how each column encodes a successive orthogonal contrast, widely used to decompose variability in multivariate and compositional data analysis.

From the perspective of matrix analysis, polar decomposition provides a natural framework for seeking more intrinsic constructions. Any square matrix admits a factorisation into an orthogonal factor and a positive semidefinite factor, and this decomposition is uniquely determined for invertible matrices [4]. When applied to structured matrices, the polar factor often reflects fundamental geometric properties of the underlying operator. In this work, this observation is exploited to construct an explicit orthogonal parametrisation of $\mathbf{1}^\perp$ based on the polar decomposition of a simple symmetric matrix. The resulting orthogonal matrix admits a closed-form expression, is symmetric, and induces an order-free decomposition of the ambient space into the span of the all-ones vector and its orthogonal complement, providing a symmetric, closed-form polar alternative to the classical Helmert matrix.

Within the same framework, it is also shown that the Helmert matrix itself can be characterised as the polar factor of a related triangular matrix. This reinterprets Helmert contrasts as a consequence of polar decomposition rather than as the outcome of Gram–Schmidt orthogonalisation and shows that the hierarchical structure of Helmert bases originates from the nonsymmetric form of the underlying generator, not from the geometry of the contrast subspace itself. The contributions of the paper are therefore twofold. First, a new symmetric, explicit, closed-form orthogonal construction associated with $\mathbf{1}^\perp$ is introduced. Second, the classical Helmert matrix is reinterpreted via a polar-decomposition characterisation, placing both constructions within a unified and transparent matrix-analytic framework. Here, the intrinsic character refers to uniqueness as the polar factor of a fixed matrix and invariance with respect to ordering or algorithmic choices, rather than to optimality or universality among all possible representations.

To clarify the structural implications of these results, two illustrative examples are included, showing how different orthonormal bases of the same subspace induce different geometric organisations. These examples are not intended as applications, but as concrete instances highlighting how the choice of orthonormal basis affects the organisation of the contrast subspace.

The paper is organised as follows. Section 2 introduces notation and basic facts on polar decomposition and rank-one perturbations. Section 3 presents the symmetric matrix and derives a closed-form expression for its polar factor. Section 4 reinterprets the Helmert matrix within the same framework. Sections 5 and 6 provide illustrative examples, and Section 7 discusses the structural implications of the results and provides concluding remarks.

2. Preliminaries and notation

This section introduces the notation and basic concepts required throughout the paper. We restrict attention to finite-dimensional real vector spaces.

2.1 Notation

For a positive integer n , let \mathbb{R}^n denote the Euclidean space equipped with the standard inner product

$$\langle x, y \rangle = x^\top y, \quad x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n,$$

and the associated Euclidean norm $\|x\| = \sqrt{x^\top x}$.

The identity matrix of order n is denoted by \mathbf{I}_n , and the vector of ones by $\mathbf{1}_n$. When the dimension is clear from the context, the subscript will be omitted.

Given a matrix \mathbf{M} , its transpose is denoted by \mathbf{M}^\top . A matrix \mathbf{Q} is orthogonal if $\mathbf{Q}^\top \mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{I}$.

For a vector $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, we denote by

$$\mathbf{1}^\perp = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n: \mathbf{1}^\top x = 0\}$$

the subspace orthogonal to the all-ones vector.

2.2 Polar decomposition

Any square matrix $\mathbf{M} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ admits a polar decomposition [4] of the form

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{U}|\mathbf{M}|,$$

where $|\mathbf{M}| = (\mathbf{M}^\top \mathbf{M})^{1/2}$ is positive semidefinite and \mathbf{U} is orthogonal on the range of \mathbf{M} . When \mathbf{M} is invertible, \mathbf{U} is uniquely determined and orthogonal.

We denote by

$$\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{M}) = \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{M}^\top \mathbf{M})^{-1/2}$$

the orthogonal factor of the polar decomposition whenever it is well defined.

If \mathbf{M} is symmetric, then $\mathbf{M}^\top \mathbf{M} = \mathbf{M}^2$, and the polar factor reduces to

$$\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{M}) = \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{M}^2)^{-1/2}.$$

In this case, $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{M})$ is symmetric and orthogonal, hence an involutory operator representing an orthogonal reflection.

2.3 Rank-one updates and spectral structure

Several constructions in this paper rely on matrices of the form

$$\mathbf{I}_n + \alpha \mathbf{J}_n, \quad \mathbf{J}_n = \mathbf{1}_n \mathbf{1}_n^\top,$$

where \mathbf{J}_n is the rank-one matrix of all ones.

The spectral structure of \mathbf{J}_n is elementary: it has eigenvalue n along the direction $\mathbf{1}_n$, and eigenvalue 0 with multiplicity $n - 1$ on $\mathbf{1}_n^\perp$. Consequently, $\mathbf{I}_n + \alpha \mathbf{J}_n$ has eigenvalue $1 + \alpha n$ along $\mathbf{1}_n$ and eigenvalue 1 on $\mathbf{1}_n^\perp$.

Whenever $1 + \alpha n > 0$, the inverse square root of $\mathbf{I}_n + \alpha \mathbf{J}_n$ is well defined and acts as

$$(\mathbf{I}_n + \alpha \mathbf{J}_n)^{-1/2} x = \begin{cases} (1 + \alpha n)^{-1/2} x & x \in \text{span}(\mathbf{1}_n) \\ x, & x \in \mathbf{1}_n^\perp \end{cases}$$

This operator admits a closed-form representation as a rank-one correction of the identity, a fact that will be exploited in subsequent sections.

Hence, $(\mathbf{I}_n + \alpha \mathbf{J}_n)^{-1/2}$ can be written as:

$$(\mathbf{I}_n + \alpha \mathbf{J}_n)^{-1/2} = \mathbf{I}_n + \beta \mathbf{1}_n \mathbf{1}_n^\top,$$

for some scalar β , which depends on α and n .

2.4 Orthogonal decompositions induced by linear constraints

The subspace $\mathbf{1}^\perp$ is the central object of the present work. It arises naturally as the kernel of the linear functional $x \mapsto \mathbf{1}^\top x$ and defines the orthogonal complement of the span of $\mathbf{1}$.

Any orthogonal matrix whose first column is proportional to $\mathbf{1}$ induces an orthonormal basis of $\mathbf{1}^\perp$ through its remaining columns. Different choices of such matrices correspond to different parametrisations of the same subspace.

The focus of this paper is on explicit constructions of orthogonal matrices that realise this decomposition in closed form and possess additional structural properties, such as symmetry or invariance with respect to coordinate ordering.

3. The matrix \mathbf{A}_K and its polar factor

In this section we introduce a simple structured matrix whose polar factor admits an explicit closed-form expression and yields a symmetric orthogonal parametrisation of the subspace orthogonal to the all-ones vector. This construction constitutes the main methodological contribution of the paper.

3.1 Definition and basic properties of \mathbf{A}_K

Let $K \geq 1$ be an integer and define the matrix

$$\mathbf{A}_K = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \mathbf{1}_K^\top \\ \mathbf{1}_K & -\mathbf{I}_K \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(K+1) \times (K+1)},$$

where $\mathbf{1}_K \in \mathbb{R}^K$ denotes the vector of ones and \mathbf{I}_K the identity matrix of order K .

The matrix \mathbf{A}_K is symmetric and has a simple block structure. Its first row and column encode the aggregation of the remaining components, while the lower-right block corresponds to a negative identity. This form will allow an explicit computation of its polar factor.

Since \mathbf{A}_K is symmetric, its polar decomposition reduces to

$$\mathbf{A}_K = \mathbf{U}_{K+1} |\mathbf{A}_K|, \quad \mathbf{U}_{K+1} = \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{A}_K) = \mathbf{A}_K (\mathbf{A}_K^2)^{-1/2},$$

where \mathbf{U}_{K+1} is an orthogonal matrix and $|\mathbf{A}_K|$ denotes the positive semidefinite factor.

A direct calculation yields

$$\mathbf{A}_K^2 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 + K & \mathbf{0}^\top \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I}_K + \mathbf{J}_K \end{bmatrix},$$

where $\mathbf{J}_K = \mathbf{1}_K \mathbf{1}_K^\top$ is the rank-one all-ones matrix.

3.2 Spectral and variational motivation of \mathbf{A}_K

The matrix \mathbf{A}_K has a simple and informative structure. It is a symmetric arrowhead matrix with diagonal entries $1, -1, \dots, -1$ and a rank-one coupling between the first coordinate and the remaining K coordinates through the all-ones vector. This is the simplest symmetric operator that (i) treats the last K coordinates isotropically and (ii) couples them to a single aggregate direction, so that the invariant splitting it induces is precisely

$$\mathbb{R}^{K+1} = \text{span}(\mathbf{1}) \oplus \mathbf{1}^\perp$$

The spectral structure follows from this decomposition. For any $v \in \mathbb{R}^K$ with $\mathbf{1}_K^\top v = 0$

$$\mathbf{A}_K \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ v \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -v \end{bmatrix},$$

So -1 is an eigenvalue with multiplicity $K - 1$ on the subspace $\{\mathbf{0}\} \oplus \mathbf{1}_K^\perp$. On the two-dimensional subspace spanned by $\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \mathbf{1}_K \end{bmatrix}$ and $\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ -\mathbf{1}_K \end{bmatrix}$, the restriction of \mathbf{A}_K has eigenvalues $+\sqrt{K+1}$ and $-\sqrt{K+1}$, giving the spectrum

$$\sigma(\mathbf{A}_K) = \{-1 \text{ (mult. } K - 1), +\sqrt{K+1}, -\sqrt{K+1}\}$$

This spectral picture connects directly with the variational characterisation of the polar factor. By the Fan–Hoffman theorem [5], the orthogonal polar factor of a real matrix \mathbf{M} is the unique orthogonal matrix closest to \mathbf{M} in the Frobenius norm, that is, the unique solution of the associated orthogonal Procrustes problem. In the present setting, the polar factor $\mathbf{U}_{K+1} = \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{A}_K)$ is therefore the orthogonal matrix that best approximates the symmetric arrowhead generator \mathbf{A}_K and, because \mathbf{A}_K is symmetric, it acts spectrally as $+1$ on the eigenspace associated with $+\sqrt{K+1}$ and as -1 on its orthogonal complement. Thus \mathbf{U}_{K+1} is an intrinsic reflection: it fixes the one-dimensional subspace aligned with the aggregate direction and flips its orthogonal complement, selecting a

unique orthogonal representative of the decomposition $\mathbb{R}^{K+1} = \text{span}(\mathbf{1}) \oplus \mathbf{1}^\perp$ without any arbitrary choice of vector or sequential orthogonalisation.

3.3 Closed-form expression of the polar factor

Proposition 3.1. The polar factor of \mathbf{A}_K is given by

$$\mathbf{U}_{K+1} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} \mathbf{1}_K^\top \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} \mathbf{1}_K & -\mathbf{I}_K - \rho_K \mathbf{J}_K \end{bmatrix}, \quad \rho_K = \frac{1 - \sqrt{K+1}}{K\sqrt{K+1}}.$$

Proof

The spectral structure of $\mathbf{I}_K + \mathbf{J}_K$ is elementary: it has eigenvalue $1 + K$ along the direction $\mathbf{1}_K$ and eigenvalue 1 with multiplicity $K - 1$ on the orthogonal complement. Consequently, its inverse square root acts as $(1+K)^{-1/2}$ on $\mathbf{1}_K$ and as the identity on $\mathbf{1}_K^\perp$.

This behaviour can be represented in closed form using a rank-one correction:

$$(\mathbf{I}_K + \mathbf{J}_K)^{-1/2} = \mathbf{I}_K + \rho_K \mathbf{J}_K$$

A complete derivation of this identity, exploiting the rank-one structure of \mathbf{J}_K and applying the Sherman–Morrison formula [6] for rank-one updates, is presented in Appendix A.

Combining these results, the inverse square root of \mathbf{A}_K^2 is

$$(\mathbf{A}_K^2)^{-1/2} = \begin{bmatrix} 1+K & \mathbf{0}^\top \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I}_K + \mathbf{J}_K \end{bmatrix}^{-1/2} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} & \mathbf{0}^\top \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I}_K + \rho_K \mathbf{J}_K \end{bmatrix}$$

Multiplying by \mathbf{A}_K then yields the polar factor:

$$\mathbf{U}_{K+1} = \mathbf{A}_K (\mathbf{A}_K^2)^{-1/2} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \mathbf{1}_K^\top \\ \mathbf{1}_K & -\mathbf{I}_K \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} & \mathbf{0}^\top \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I}_K + \rho_K \mathbf{J}_K \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} & \mathbf{1}_K^\top (\mathbf{I}_K + \rho_K \mathbf{J}_K) \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} \mathbf{1}_K & -\mathbf{I}_K (\mathbf{I}_K + \rho_K \mathbf{J}_K) \end{bmatrix}$$

Using the identity $\mathbf{1}_K^\top (\mathbf{I}_K + \rho_K \mathbf{J}_K) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} \mathbf{1}_K^\top$, we recover the expression in the proposition, completing the proof:

$$\mathbf{U}_{K+1} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} \mathbf{1}_K^\top \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} \mathbf{1}_K & -\mathbf{I}_K - \rho_K \mathbf{J}_K \end{bmatrix}$$

To make the structure of \mathbf{U}_{K+1} immediately apparent, we can expand it explicitly as

$$\mathbf{U}_{K+1} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} & \cdots & \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} & -1 - \rho_K & -\rho_K & \cdots & -\rho_K \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} & -\rho_K & -1 - \rho_K & \cdots & -\rho_K \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} & -\rho_K & -\rho_K & \cdots & -1 - \rho_K \end{bmatrix}$$

where the pattern in the lower $K \times K$ block clearly shows the symmetric structure and the contribution of the rank-one correction. This explicit form allows the reader to appreciate the order-free, symmetric nature of the constructed polar factor.

3.4 Structural properties and interpretation

The matrix \mathbf{U}_{K+1} enjoys several notable properties.

First, the construction admits an explicit closed-form expression. The polar analysis developed above yields an analytic formula for \mathbf{U}_{K+1} , allowing its construction in a single step, without recourse to recursive, sequential, or algorithmic procedures. This distinguishes the present approach from classical constructions based on Gram–Schmidt orthogonalisation or Householder transformations, where the orthonormal basis is obtained iteratively.

Second, it is orthogonal and symmetric. Hence it represents an involutory orthogonal transformation, that is, a reflection. This reflection acts globally on the ambient space and fixes the decomposition into the span of the all-ones vector and its orthogonal complement, rather than rotating the contrast subspace within itself. This distinguishes it from classical constructions of orthonormal bases of constrained subspaces, which typically rely on sequential orthogonalisation and do not produce symmetric operators.

Third, the first column of \mathbf{U}_{K+1} is proportional to the all-ones vector. The remaining columns form an orthonormal basis of the subspace

$$\mathbf{1}^\perp = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{K+1}; \mathbf{1}^\top x = 0\}.$$

This yields the explicit orthogonal decomposition

$$\mathbb{R}^{K+1} = \text{span}(\mathbf{1}) \oplus \mathbf{1}^\perp,$$

with both components realised in closed form.

Fourth, the construction is order-free and non-hierarchical. No ordering of the coordinates is imposed, and no iterative procedure is involved. This order-free property is structural: any permutation $\mathbf{\Pi}$ of the last K coordinates satisfy

$$\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{\Pi}^\top \mathbf{A}_K \mathbf{\Pi}) = \mathbf{\Pi}^\top \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{A}_K) \mathbf{\Pi},$$

showing that the parametrisation is invariant under reorderings that preserve the structure of the generator. Moreover, the basis of $\mathbf{1}^\perp$ is determined uniquely by the polar decomposition of a fixed symmetric matrix, which confers an intrinsic character to the resulting orthonormal representation.

In addition to the properties discussed above, it is important to clarify the precise algebraic nature of the orthogonal matrix \mathbf{U}_{K+1} .

\mathbf{U}_{K+1} is symmetric and orthogonal, with a one-dimensional eigenspace associated with the eigenvalue $+1$ and the orthogonal complement associated with the eigenvalue -1 . It thus acts as an involutory operator representing a reflection on the subspace orthogonal to the $+1$ eigenspace. This observation does not trivialise the present construction: \mathbf{U}_{K+1} arises uniquely as the orthogonal polar factor of the fixed symmetric matrix \mathbf{A}_K , rather than being defined via an arbitrary choice of vector as in the classical Householder approach [7].

From this perspective, the construction singles out an intrinsic orthogonal representative associated with the decomposition

$$\mathbb{R}^{K+1} = \text{span}(\mathbf{1}) \oplus \mathbf{1}^\perp,$$

where this intrinsic character refers to uniqueness as a polar factor and invariance with respect to ordering or auxiliary selections. This interpretation distinguishes the present construction from standard Householder reflections used as computational tools, while preserving their fundamental algebraic nature.

These properties position \mathbf{U}_{K+1} as a natural symmetric alternative to classical orthonormal bases of $\mathbf{1}^\perp$. In the following section we show that the well-known Helmert matrix arises from an analogous polar construction, which allows both matrices to be analysed within a unified framework.

4. The Helmert matrix revisited via polar decomposition

In this section we show that the classical Helmert matrix arises naturally as the polar factor of a simple structured matrix. This result places Helmert-type constructions within the same polar decomposition framework as the symmetric matrix introduced in Section 3, and clarifies their structural relationship.

4.1 Definition of the matrix \mathbf{B}_K

Let $K \geq 1$ and define the matrix

$$\mathbf{B}_K = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \mathbf{1}_K^\top \\ \mathbf{1}_K & \mathbf{T}_K \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(K+1) \times (K+1)},$$

where $\mathbf{T}_K \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times K}$ is the upper triangular matrix given by

$$\mathbf{T}_K = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 \\ 0 & -2 & 1 & \cdots & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -3 & \cdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & -K \end{bmatrix}.$$

The matrix \mathbf{B}_K will be shown to act as a generating operator whose orthogonal polar factor coincides with the Helmert matrix under the convention adopted in this work. Its nonsymmetric structure encodes an explicit hierarchical structure through the triangular block \mathbf{T}_K . This choice ensures that the first column is proportional to the all-ones vector, so that the resulting polar factor has the correct first column for contrast subspaces, while the triangular block induces a sequential, ordered basis of $\mathbf{1}^\perp$. Such matrices arise naturally in sequential orthogonalisation procedures: applying Gram–Schmidt to the columns of \mathbf{B}_K recovers the classical Helmert contrasts. This construction makes explicit the hierarchical relationships among the contrast directions and highlights the dependence of the resulting orthonormal basis on the ordering of the coordinates.

4.2 Spectral and variational interpretation of \mathbf{B}_K

The generating role of \mathbf{B}_K is reflected in its spectral and variational properties. Unlike the symmetric matrix \mathbf{A}_K , the present construction is nonsymmetric and encodes an explicit hierarchy through its upper triangular block \mathbf{T}_K . This block implements a sequential contrast mechanism, where each new coordinate is compared against cumulative aggregates of the preceding ones, so that \mathbf{B}_K acts as a discrete first-order difference generator adapted to the contrast subspace.

This hierarchical structure becomes transparent at the level of the Gram matrix. A direct computation (see Section 4.3) shows that

$$\mathbf{B}_K^\top \mathbf{B}_K = \begin{bmatrix} K+1 & \mathbf{0}^\top \\ \mathbf{0} & \text{diag}(j(j+1))_{j=1}^K \end{bmatrix},$$

so the columns of \mathbf{B}_K are mutually orthogonal with singular values

$$\sigma_1 = \sqrt{K+1}, \quad \sigma_{j+1} = \sqrt{j(j+1)}, \quad j = 1, \dots, K.$$

For $K \geq 2$, the spectral condition number in the Euclidean norm is therefore

$$\kappa_2(\mathbf{B}_K) = \frac{\max_{1 \leq j \leq K} \sqrt{j(j+1)}}{\min\{\sqrt{K+1}, \sqrt{2}\}} = \sqrt{\frac{K(K+1)}{2}},$$

so \mathbf{B}_K provides a well-defined but increasingly ill-conditioned generating family as the dimension grows.

Within this framework, the polar decomposition has a particularly clear meaning. The orthogonal polar factor

$$\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{B}_K) = \mathbf{B}_K(\mathbf{B}_K^\top \mathbf{B}_K)^{-1/2}$$

performs an exact orthogonalisation and normalisation of the hierarchical contrast scheme encoded by \mathbf{B}_K , removing the anisotropic scaling induced by the triangular generator \mathbf{T}_K and produces an orthonormal basis in closed form. The main point of this section is that this orthogonal factor is precisely the classical Helmert matrix \mathbf{H}_{K+1} so Helmert is the polar factor of the triangular generator \mathbf{B}_K rather than merely the outcome of a Gram–Schmidt procedure.

4.3 Polar factor of \mathbf{B}_K

Proposition 4.1. The orthogonal polar factor $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{B}_K)$ coincides with the classical Helmert matrix \mathbf{H}_{K+1} . In particular, its first column is proportional to the all-ones vector, and its remaining columns form an orthonormal basis of the contrast subspace with the usual triangular Helmert structure. Orthogonality follows from the polar decomposition.

Proof

Since \mathbf{B}_K is invertible, it admits a unique polar decomposition

$$\mathbf{B}_K = \mathbf{Q}_{K+1} |\mathbf{B}_K|, \quad \mathbf{Q}_{K+1} = \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{B}_K) = \mathbf{B}_K(\mathbf{B}_K^\top \mathbf{B}_K)^{-1/2}$$

A direct computation shows that the Gram matrix of the generator is diagonal:

$$\mathbf{B}_K^\top \mathbf{B}_K = \begin{bmatrix} K+1 & \mathbf{0}^\top \\ \mathbf{0} & \text{diag}(j(j+1))_{j=1}^K \end{bmatrix},$$

Since this Gram matrix is diagonal, its inverse square root is also diagonal, and the orthogonal polar factor can be expressed as a column-wise rescaling of the generator:

$$\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{B}_K) = \mathbf{B}_K \mathbf{D},$$

where

$$\mathbf{D} = \text{diag}((K+1)^{-1/2}, (1 \cdot 2)^{-1/2}, \dots, (K(K+1))^{-1/2})$$

contains the reciprocals of the column norms. Each column of $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{B}_K)$ is thus the corresponding column of \mathbf{B}_K normalised to unit length, making explicit how the hierarchical pattern encoded in the triangular generator is preserved while enforcing orthonormality.

Multiplying by \mathbf{B}_K in this way removes the anisotropic scaling induced by the triangular block \mathbf{T}_K and produces an orthonormal basis in closed form. The lower $K \times K$ block exhibits the characteristic lower-triangular structure of the Helmert contrasts.

For concreteness, consider $K = 4$:

$$\mathbf{B}_4 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & -2 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & -3 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -4 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{B}_4^\top \mathbf{B}_4 = \text{diag}(5, 2, 6, 12, 20).$$

The corresponding diagonal scaling matrix is

$$\mathbf{D} = \text{diag}(5^{-1/2}, 2^{-1/2}, 6^{-1/2}, 12^{-1/2}, 20^{-1/2}),$$

so that the polar factor is

$$\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{B}_4) = \mathbf{B}_4 \mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/\sqrt{5} & 1/\sqrt{2} & 1/\sqrt{6} & 1/\sqrt{12} & 1/\sqrt{20} \\ 1/\sqrt{5} & -1/\sqrt{2} & 1/\sqrt{6} & 1/\sqrt{12} & 1/\sqrt{20} \\ 1/\sqrt{5} & 0 & -2/\sqrt{6} & 1/\sqrt{12} & 1/\sqrt{20} \\ 1/\sqrt{5} & 0 & 0 & -3/\sqrt{12} & 1/\sqrt{20} \\ 1/\sqrt{5} & 0 & 0 & 0 & -4/\sqrt{20} \end{bmatrix}.$$

This matrix coincides exactly with the classical Helmert matrix \mathbf{H}_5 . More generally, for arbitrary K , $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{B}_K)$ produces \mathbf{H}_{K+1} , showing that Helmert contrasts arise naturally as the polar factor of the triangular generator rather than as a consequence of a sequential Gram–Schmidt procedure.

In the literature, \mathbf{H}_{K+1} is usually obtained by applying Gram–Schmidt to specially prepared generating matrices, often verified numerically or for small K [2,8,9]. A few closed-form constructions have been proposed for particular parameter choices [10,11], but none explicitly identify the Helmert matrix as the polar factor of a structured triangular generator.

A formal derivation showing that \mathbf{H}_{K+1} can also be obtained by applying Gram–Schmidt to the columns of the symmetric matrix \mathbf{A}_K is provided in Appendix B.1, while Appendix B.2 shows the derivation by applying Gram–Schmidt to the columns of \mathbf{B}_K . This complements the polar decomposition approach, situating Helmert matrices alongside generalized Helmert–Ledermann constructions [12] and highlighting that $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{B}_K)$ is singled out as the unique orthogonal solution of a Procrustes problem for the fixed triangular generator, whereas $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{A}_K)$ provides a symmetric, intrinsic alternative for the same contrast subspace.

4.4 Structural interpretation

Proposition 4.1 yields a concise structural statement: the classical Helmert matrix is the orthogonal polar factor of the triangular generator \mathbf{B}_K . This reinterprets Helmert contrasts as the solution of an orthogonal Procrustes problem for a specific structured matrix, rather than as an artefact of a particular Gram–Schmidt path.

This polar viewpoint has several consequences. First, it embeds Helmert matrices into the general theory of polar decomposition and structured operators, aligning them with the same framework used for the symmetric construction based on \mathbf{A}_K . Second, it makes explicit that the hierarchical, order-dependent nature of Helmert contrasts is inherited directly from the triangular block \mathbf{T}_K : the hierarchy does not come from the contrast subspace itself, but from the chosen nonsymmetric generator. Third, when compared with the symmetric polar factor $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{A}_K)$, which yields an order-free reflection, the matrix $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{B}_K)$ appears as a structure-induced basis: both matrices parametrise the same contrast subspace, but one is intrinsic and symmetric, while the other encodes a built-in hierarchy through its triangular form.

4.5 Comparison with the symmetric polar construction

The matrices $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{A}_K)$ and $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{B}_K)$ provide two explicit orthogonal bases of the same subspace $\mathbf{1}^\perp$. Their difference lies not in the subspace itself, but in the manner in which it is organised.

The Helmert matrix reflects a sequential, order-dependent construction. Its basis vectors correspond to successive contrasts between coordinates, and their form depends explicitly on the chosen ordering. By contrast, the matrix $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{A}_K)$ is symmetric and order-free. Its basis of $\mathbf{1}^\perp$ is determined uniquely by the polar decomposition of a fixed symmetric matrix, without reference to any hierarchy among the coordinates.

This comparison highlights that Helmert matrices are not intrinsic representatives of the contrast subspace, but rather one possible choice within a broader class of orthonormal parametrisations. The symmetric polar construction introduced in this work provides a closed-form, non-hierarchical alternative within the same theoretical framework.

Sections 3 and 4 show that two classical constructions of orthonormal bases of $\mathbf{1}^\perp$ arise naturally as polar factors of structured matrices. In both cases, the resulting orthogonal matrices realise the same decomposition

$$\mathbb{R}^{K+1} = \text{span}(\mathbf{1}) \oplus \mathbf{1}^\perp,$$

but differ in their structural properties.

The symmetric matrix $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{A}_K)$ is uniquely determined by the polar decomposition of a fixed symmetric matrix and yields an order-free, non-hierarchical parametrisation of $\mathbf{1}^\perp$. By contrast, the Helmert matrix $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{B}_K)$ inherits a hierarchical structure from the triangular form of \mathbf{B}_K and depends explicitly on a chosen ordering of the coordinates.

Since both matrices provide orthonormal bases of the same subspace, any vector in $\mathbf{1}^\perp$ admits representations in either basis. Comparing these representations offers a concrete way to visualise the structural consequences of choosing one parametrisation or the other, without introducing additional assumptions or altering the underlying subspace.

5. Example I: Order-free parametrisation of the contrast subspace

In this section we illustrate, through a concrete algebraic example, the difference between two orthonormal parametrisations of $\mathbf{1}^\perp$ introduced in Sections 3 and 4. The purpose is to visualise how distinct orthonormal bases of the same subspace induce different structural and quantitative representations.

5.1 The contrast subspace

Let $n = K + 1$ and consider the subspace

$$\mathbf{1}^\perp = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n: \mathbf{1}^\top x = 0\}.$$

This subspace has dimension K and is defined independently of any particular choice of coordinates. It is the orthogonal complement of $\text{span}(\mathbf{1})$ and plays a central role whenever a linear constraint of the form $\mathbf{1}^\top x = \text{constant}$ is imposed.

Any orthogonal matrix whose first column is proportional to $\mathbf{1}$ induces an orthonormal basis of $\mathbf{1}^\perp$ through its remaining columns. Different choices of such matrices correspond to distinct orthonormal parametrisations of the same subspace. This situation arises, for example, in the construction of orthogonal contrasts in one-way ANOVA, where alternative bases are used to decompose between-group variability in algebraically equivalent ways [3,13].

In the following subsections we compare two such parametrisations, both derived from polar decompositions of structured matrices, in order to highlight the structural consequences of choosing one orthonormal basis over another.

5.2 Representation under two orthonormal parametrisations

Let $x \in \mathbf{1}^\perp$ be a fixed non-zero vector. Its coordinates depend on the choice of orthonormal basis used to parametrise the contrast subspace.

Under the Helmert parametrisation, the coordinates of x are given by

$$\alpha^{(H)} = \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{B}_K)^\top x.$$

Due to the triangular structure of the Helmert matrix, the components of $\alpha^{(H)}$ reflect a hierarchical organisation, with each entry corresponding to a successive contrast. Therefore, the numerical values of these coordinates depend explicitly on the ordering of the indices.

Under the symmetric polar parametrisation introduced in Section 3, the same vector x is represented by

$$\alpha^{(U)} = \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{A}_K)^\top x.$$

Since $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{A}_K)$ is symmetric and arises as the orthogonal polar factor of a fixed symmetric matrix, this parametrisation does not impose any ordering or hierarchy. All directions in $\mathbf{1}^\perp$ are treated on an equal footing.

To compare the two representations quantitatively, we consider the following metrics:

- the maximum absolute coordinate,

$$\alpha_\infty^{(H)} = \max_j |\alpha_j^{(H)}|, \quad \alpha_\infty^{(U)} = \max_j |\alpha_j^{(U)}|,$$

- and the energy distribution across coordinates,

$$E_j^{(H)} = \frac{(\alpha_j^{(H)})^2}{\|\alpha^{(H)}\|_2^2}, \quad E_j^{(U)} = \frac{(\alpha_j^{(U)})^2}{\|\alpha^{(U)}\|_2^2}.$$

These quantities highlight the structural contrast between the two parametrisations. In the Helmert basis, the variability of x is often concentrated in the first few contrast directions, reflecting the sequential and hierarchical nature of the construction. By contrast, the symmetric polar basis typically distributes the same information more evenly among the coordinates, with no privileged direction. This behaviour illustrates the order dependence of the Helmert parametrisation and the order-free character of the symmetric polar alternative.

5.3 Numerical illustration for $n = 4$

To make the structural difference between the two parametrisations explicit, we consider a low-dimensional example with $n = 4$ (that is, $K = 3$). In this case, the contrast subspace $\mathbf{1}^\perp \subset \mathbb{R}^4$ has dimension three.

The Helmert matrix of order four can be written as

$$\mathbf{H}_4 = \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 & 1/\sqrt{2} & 1/\sqrt{6} & 1/\sqrt{12} \\ 1/2 & -1/\sqrt{2} & 1/\sqrt{6} & 1/\sqrt{12} \\ 1/2 & 0 & -2/\sqrt{6} & 1/\sqrt{12} \\ 1/2 & 0 & 0 & -3/\sqrt{12} \end{bmatrix},$$

where the first column is proportional to the all-ones vector and the remaining columns form an orthonormal basis of $\mathbf{1}^\perp$.

By contrast, the symmetric polar construction introduced in Section 3 yields the orthogonal matrix

$$\mathbf{U}_4 = \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 & 1/2 & 1/2 & 1/2 \\ 1/2 & -5/6 & 1/6 & 1/6 \\ 1/2 & 1/6 & -5/6 & 1/6 \\ 1/2 & 1/6 & 1/6 & -5/6 \end{bmatrix}$$

which is symmetric and whose last three columns provide an order-free orthonormal basis of $\mathbf{1}^\perp$.

Consider now the vector

$$x = [1 \quad -1 \quad 0 \quad 0]^\top \in \mathbf{1}^\perp,$$

Its coordinates in the Helmert basis are given by

$$\alpha^{(H)} = \mathbf{H}_4^\top x = [0 \quad \sqrt{2} \quad 0 \quad 0]^\top,$$

so that all the variability of x is concentrated on the first contrast direction of the hierarchical basis ($E_2 = 1$).

By contrast, the coordinates of the same vector in the symmetric polar basis are

$$\alpha^{(U)} = \mathbf{U}_4^\top x = [0 \quad 4/3 \quad 1/3 \quad 1/3]^\top,$$

which distributes the same information across multiple directions in a symmetric manner ($E_2 \approx 0.889$, $E_3 \approx 0.056$, $E_4 \approx 0.056$).

Both coordinate representations correspond to the same vector in $\mathbf{1}^\perp$. The difference lies entirely in the organisation of the basis. The Helmert parametrisation assigns a privileged role to a single contrast direction, reflecting its hierarchical structure, whereas the symmetric polar parametrisation treats all directions on an equal footing. This simple example makes explicit the order dependence of the Helmert construction and the order-free nature of the symmetric polar alternative.

5.4 Structural discussion

This example demonstrates quantitatively that:

- The Helmert basis is hierarchical and order-dependent, concentrating energy in the first contrasts.
- The symmetric polar basis is order-free, distributing energy evenly, reflecting the intrinsic symmetry of the generator \mathbf{A}_K .
- These metrics provide a mathematical takeaway beyond the visual illustration, highlighting structural differences relevant for ANOVA or other applications in linearly constrained subspaces.

6. Example II: Admissible perturbations under linear constraints

This section provides a second illustrative example that clarifies the role of the proposed symmetric polar construction. Unlike the previous example, which focused on the representation of fixed vectors in $\mathbf{1}^\perp$, we now examine admissible perturbations under a linear constraint and compare two alternative parametrisations. The goal is to highlight the structural differences between hierarchical and order-free descriptions of the same admissible perturbation set.

6.1 Linear constraint and admissible directions

Let $n = K + 1$ and consider the affine hyperplane

$$\mathcal{H} = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n: \mathbf{1}^\top x = 1\}.$$

This set is a translation of the subspace $\mathbf{1}^\perp$ and represents the solution set of a linear constraint fixing the sum of the components of a vector. An additive perturbation $x \mapsto x + \delta$ preserves the constraint if and only if $\delta \in \mathbf{1}^\perp$.

Linear constraints of this type arise, for instance, in compositional data analysis, where admissible perturbations must preserve a constant sum [14–16]. Different orthonormal bases of $\mathbf{1}^\perp$ provide alternative coordinate systems to describe the same set of admissible directions.

In the following subsections we compare two such parametrisations, induced respectively by the Helmert matrix and by the symmetric polar construction introduced in Section 3, in order to highlight the structural consequences of the chosen orthonormal basis.

6.2 Parametrisation of admissible perturbations

Let $\mathbf{1}^\perp \subset \mathbb{R}^{K+1}$ denote the admissible perturbation subspace. Any perturbation $\delta \in \mathbf{1}^\perp$ can be parametrised once an orthonormal basis of this subspace is fixed.

Using the Helmert matrix $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{B}_K)$ introduced in Section 4, any admissible perturbation can be written as

$$\delta = \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{B}_K) \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \beta \end{bmatrix}, \beta \in \mathbb{R}^K,$$

where the zero in the first coordinate enforces orthogonality to $\mathbf{1}$. The components of β correspond to hierarchical contrast directions, so that perturbations tend to be concentrated in the

first few coordinates. This hierarchical organisation can be quantified by the maximum absolute coordinate $\|\beta\|_\infty$ and by the energy distribution $E_j = \beta_j^2 / \|\beta\|_2^2$.

For small dimensions (e.g., $n = 4$), these metrics typically reveal sparse representations, with most of the energy concentrated in early components.

An alternative parametrisation is obtained using the symmetric polar basis defined by $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{A}_K)$ in Section 3. In this case,

$$\delta = \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{A}_K) \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \gamma \end{bmatrix}, \gamma \in \mathbb{R}^K.$$

Since $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{A}_K)$ is symmetric and orthogonal, this parametrisation treats all directions in $\mathbf{1}^\perp$ symmetrically. No coordinate is privileged, and no hierarchy is imposed. Computing the same metrics, $\|\gamma\|_\infty$ and $E_j = \gamma_j^2 / \|\gamma\|_2^2$, confirms that the energy of a perturbation is typically distributed more evenly across components, illustrating the order-free and intrinsic character of the symmetric polar construction.

Both parametrisations generate exactly the same set of admissible perturbations, namely the subspace $\mathbf{1}^\perp$. The difference lies solely in the organisation of the coordinate system used to describe them. For a fixed dimension (for instance, $n = 4$), the two parametrisations are related by an orthogonal change of coordinates within $\mathbf{1}^\perp$, so that the same perturbation may admit markedly different coordinate representations under each basis.

6.3 Structural discussion

- The Helmert basis imposes a sequential, order-dependent structure, producing perturbations that are sparse along early contrast directions.
- The symmetric polar basis yields an order-free parametrisation, with perturbations distributed uniformly across all coordinates in $\mathbf{1}^\perp$.
- Both representations span the same subspace and are algebraically equivalent, but the coordinate organisation differs.

The choice of orthonormal basis for a linearly constrained subspace affects the interpretation and structure of perturbations. Quantitative metrics such as $\|\cdot\|_\infty$ and energy fractions E_j provide a verifiable, mathematical illustration of how Helmert induces hierarchy and sparsity, while the symmetric polar basis ensures uniform, order-independent representation.

7. Discussion

This work has presented an explicit orthogonal construction associated with the subspace orthogonal to the all-ones vector. The construction arises from the polar decomposition of a simple symmetric matrix and yields a closed-form, symmetric, and order-free parametrisation of $\mathbf{1}^\perp$.

A central point of the paper is that this construction does not introduce a new subspace or modify the underlying geometry. Rather, it provides an intrinsic orthogonal representative within the class of orthonormal parametrisations of $\mathbf{1}^\perp$. Here, the term intrinsic is understood in a precise sense: uniqueness as the orthogonal polar factor of a fixed generating matrix, together with invariance with respect to ordering or algorithmic choices. This description does not refer to optimality with respect to an external criterion, nor to universality across all possible matrix representations.

From a practical viewpoint, the availability of a closed-form symmetric polar factor has two main benefits. It enables purely symbolic manipulations in theoretical work—such as commutators, perturbation expansions or limits involving the orthogonal factor—without resorting to iterative polar algorithms or Gram–Schmidt procedures. In applications where the contrast subspace $\mathbf{1}^\perp$ plays a structural role, for instance in panel data models or compositional data analysis, the closed form also yields exact expressions for contrast coordinates and their derivatives with respect to

underlying parameters, which is useful in sensitivity analyses and in the design of constrained estimators.

From an algebraic viewpoint, the resulting matrix is an involutory orthogonal operator, that is, an orthogonal reflection. Indeed, any symmetric orthogonal operator with a one-dimensional eigenspace associated with the eigenvalue $+1$ admits such a representation. The relevance of the present construction, however, lies not in the existence of a reflection, but in the way this reflector is characterised. Rather than being defined through the explicit selection of a vector, the orthogonal operator arises uniquely as the polar factor of a fixed symmetric matrix. In this sense, the reflector is imposed by the structure of the generating operator itself, and not by an auxiliary or algorithmic choice.

This perspective admits a natural variational interpretation. The polar factor can be viewed as the unique solution of an orthogonal Procrustes problem associated with the matrix \mathbf{A}_K , that is, as the orthogonal matrix closest to \mathbf{A}_K in the Frobenius norm [5]. The symmetric and order-free nature of the resulting parametrisation follows directly from this characterisation. The decomposition

$$\mathbb{R}^{K+1} = \text{span}(\mathbf{1}) \oplus \mathbf{1}^\perp$$

is thus realised by an orthogonal operator that is selected intrinsically by polar decomposition, without recourse to sequential orthogonalisation or prescribed hierarchies.

The reinterpretation of the Helmert matrix within the same polar framework reinforces this viewpoint. By showing that Helmert contrasts arise as the polar factor of a structured triangular matrix, the analysis places a classical construction within the same unifying setting. The hierarchical nature of Helmert bases is thereby traced back to the nonsymmetric structure of the underlying matrix, rather than to any intrinsic property of the contrast subspace itself. In contrast, the symmetric construction arises from a symmetric operator and yields an order-independent parametrisation.

The two illustrative examples serve to emphasise these structural distinctions. In the first example, representations of the same vector in $\mathbf{1}^\perp$ were compared under different orthonormal bases, making explicit how a hierarchical basis organises information sequentially, while the symmetric polar basis distributes it in an order-free manner. In the second example, admissible perturbations under a linear constraint were described using both parametrisations. Although the set of admissible directions is identical in both cases, the geometric organisation induced by each basis differs in a structurally meaningful way.

The present analysis is deliberately restricted to the standard Euclidean inner product and to the equicorrelated setting associated with the all-ones vector. This restriction is not a limitation of the polar-decomposition framework itself, but a choice aimed at isolating its structural consequences without introducing additional geometric or statistical layers. Extensions to weighted inner products lead naturally to weighted contrast systems, weighted versions of Helmert bases, and connections with generalized least squares, generalized linear models, and compositional data analysis. While these settings are mathematically compatible with the polar and Procrustes viewpoints developed here, their treatment requires a distinct focus on metric-induced geometry and statistical interpretation and therefore lies beyond the scope of the present work.

From this viewpoint, the contribution of the paper is not the introduction of a new orthogonal operator, but the identification of a unifying polar-decomposition principle that explains how standard constructions of orthogonal reflections and hierarchical contrast bases emerge intrinsically from different structured matrices. More broadly, the results suggest that polar decomposition provides a useful organising framework for the study of orthogonal parametrisations of linearly constrained subspaces. Different structured matrices may lead, via their polar factors, to different structure-induced orthogonal bases of the same subspace, each reflecting the symmetry or hierarchy encoded in the original operator.

The constructions presented in this work are purely algebraic. In particular, the symmetric polar construction admits an explicit closed-form expression. No claims are made regarding numerical

stability or computational efficiency in finite-precision arithmetic, and comparisons with iterative orthogonalisation procedures fall beyond the scope of the present study.

At an implementation level, while Helmert matrices are commonly implemented using sequential orthogonalisation procedures in widely used software environments—such as Python via “`scipy.linalg.helmert`” [17], R via “`stats::contr.helmert`” [18], and MATLAB via “`helmert`” [19]—these implementations adopt the same column-oriented convention for Helmert contrasts as the one used throughout this work. Within this common operational setting, the symmetric closed-form polar factor introduced here allows a direct, order-independent computation. This closed-form construction is easily vectorised and suitable for parallel implementations, highlighting its practical advantage over traditional sequential methods.

Appendix A. Closed-form derivation of $(\mathbf{I}_K + \mathbf{J}_K)^{-1/2}$

From the Sherman-Morrison formula [6] for a rank-one perturbation of the identity,

$$(\mathbf{I} + \alpha uu^\top)^{-1} = \mathbf{I} - \frac{\alpha}{1 + \alpha u^\top u} uu^\top,$$

we obtain, in the present case with $\alpha = 1$ and $u = \mathbf{1}_K$:

$$(\mathbf{I}_K + \mathbf{J}_K)^{-1} = \mathbf{I}_K - \frac{1}{1+K} \mathbf{J}_K \tag{A.1}$$

As discussed in section 2.3, we seek an inverse square root of the form

$$(\mathbf{I}_K + \mathbf{J}_K)^{-1/2} = \mathbf{I}_K + \beta \mathbf{J}_K$$

Squaring this expression and using the rank-one property $\mathbf{J}_K^2 = K\mathbf{J}_K$ yields

$$(\mathbf{I}_K + \mathbf{J}_K)^{-1} = \mathbf{I}_K + 2\beta \mathbf{J}_K + K\beta^2 \mathbf{J}_K \tag{A.2}$$

Comparing Eq. (A.1) and Eq. (A.2) and solving the resulting quadratic equation for β gives the unique solution that reproduces the correct eigenvalue along $\mathbf{1}_K$:

$$\beta = \rho_K = \frac{1 - \sqrt{1 + K}}{K\sqrt{1 + K}}$$

Hence,

$$(\mathbf{I}_K + \mathbf{J}_K)^{-1/2} = \mathbf{I}_K + \rho_K \mathbf{J}_K$$

which is the expression used in Section 3.3 to construct the inverse square root of \mathbf{A}_K^2 and, consequently, the polar factor $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{A}_K)$.

Appendix B. Gram–Schmidt derivations

This appendix collects standard, but rarely written-out, Gram–Schmidt derivations that justify the closed-form expressions used in Sections 3 and 4. Subsection B.1 applies Gram–Schmidt to the columns of \mathbf{A}_K in the order in which they are defined, showing that the resulting orthogonal matrix coincides exactly with the Helmert matrix under the convention adopted in this work. Subsection B.2 performs the same analysis for \mathbf{B}_K , recovering again the classical Helmert matrix and its characteristic triangular structure. These details are included for completeness; the main results rely on the polar decomposition framework developed in the body of the paper.

B.1. Gram–Schmidt applied to the columns of \mathbf{A}_K

Recall that

$$\mathbf{A}_K = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \mathbf{1}_K^\top \\ \mathbf{1}_K & -\mathbf{I}_K \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(K+1) \times (K+1)},$$

where $\mathbf{1}_K \in \mathbb{R}^K$ denotes the vector of ones and \mathbf{I}_K the identity of order K . Let a_1, \dots, a_{K+1} denote the columns of \mathbf{A}_K . Explicitly,

$$a_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \mathbf{1}_K \end{bmatrix}, \quad a_{j+1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ -e_j \end{bmatrix}, \quad j = 1, \dots, K,$$

Where e_j is the j -th canonical vector in \mathbb{R}^K .

We apply the classical Gram–Schmidt procedure to the ordered family $[a_1, \dots, a_{K+1}]$ in the standard inner product of \mathbb{R}^{K+1} .

Step 1. First vector. Set $u_1 = a_1$. Its squared norm is

$$\|u_1\|^2 = K + 1.$$

Hence, the first orthonormal vector is

$$q_1 = \frac{u_1}{\|u_1\|} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \mathbf{1}_K \end{bmatrix},$$

which is proportional to the all-ones vector in \mathbb{R}^{K+1} .

Step 2. Remaining vectors. For $j = 1, \dots, K$, consider the column a_{j+1} . Its projection onto q_1 is

$$\langle a_{j+1}, q_1 \rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} (1 + \mathbf{1}_K^\top (-e_j)) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{K+1}} (1 - 1) = 0$$

Thus, each a_{j+1} is already orthogonal to q_1 , and

$$u_{j+1} = a_{j+1} - \langle a_{j+1}, q_1 \rangle q_1 = a_{j+1}.$$

We next examine the mutual inner products of the vectors a_2, \dots, a_{K+1} .

For $j \neq \ell$,

$$\langle a_{j+1}, a_{\ell+1} \rangle = 1 \cdot 1 + (-e_j)^\top (-e_\ell) = 1 + \delta_{j\ell} = 1,$$

while

$$\|a_{j+1}\|^2 = 1 + \|e_j\|^2 = 2,$$

independently of j .

Hence, the family $\{a_2, \dots, a_{K+1}\}$ consists of K vectors in \mathbb{R}^{K+1} with equal norms and constant pairwise inner product, spanning the subspace

$$\mathbf{1}^\perp = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{K+1} : \mathbf{1}^\top x = 0\}.$$

When Gram–Schmidt is applied to this family in the order induced by the definition of \mathbf{A}_K , a rigid pattern emerges. At each step, the orthogonalisation subtracts the average of the previously processed components, producing a vector whose first $j - 1$ entries are equal and whose j -th entry compensates their sum, while all subsequent entries vanish. After normalisation, this yields precisely the classical Helmert contrast structure.

B.2. Gram–Schmidt applied to the columns of \mathbf{B}_K

Recall that

$$\mathbf{B}_K = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \mathbf{1}_K^\top \\ \mathbf{1}_K & \mathbf{T}_K \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(K+1) \times (K+1)},$$

where

$$\mathbf{T}_K = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 \\ 0 & -2 & 1 & \cdots & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -3 & \cdots & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & -K \end{bmatrix}$$

is upper triangular. Denote again by b_1, \dots, b_{K+1} the columns of \mathbf{B}_K . By construction,

$$b_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \mathbf{1}_K \end{bmatrix},$$

and for $j = 1, \dots, K$, the $(j + 1)$ -th column has the form

$$b_{j+1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \mathbf{t}^{(j)} \end{bmatrix},$$

where $\mathbf{t}^{(j)}$ is the j -th column of \mathbf{T}_K . The block structure of $\mathbf{B}_K^\top \mathbf{B}_K$ shows that the b_{j+1} are mutually orthogonal with norms

$$\|b_1\|^2 = K + 1, \quad \|b_{j+1}\|^2 = j(j + 1), \quad j = 1, \dots, K$$

Since the columns of \mathbf{B}_K are already mutually orthogonal, the Gram–Schmidt procedure requires no subtraction of projections and reduces to a simple column-wise normalisation.

Step 1. First vector. Set $v_1 = b_1$. Then

$$h_1 = \frac{v_1}{\|v_1\|} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{K + 1}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \mathbf{1}_K \end{bmatrix},$$

so the first orthonormal vector coincides with the one obtained from \mathbf{A}_K and with the first column of the Helmert matrix.

Step 2. Remaining vectors. For $j = 1, \dots, K$, define

$$v_{j+1} = b_{j+1}, \quad h_{j+1} = \frac{v_{j+1}}{\|v_{j+1}\|} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{j(j + 1)}} b_{j+1}.$$

Writing h_{j+1} explicitly in coordinates yields the Helmert contrast pattern associated with the convention adopted in this work: the $(j+1)$ -th column has its first j entries equal to $1/\sqrt{j(j + 1)}$, its $(j+1)$ -th entry equal to $-j/\sqrt{j(j + 1)}$, and zeros elsewhere.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work, the author used ChatGPT (OpenAI, version 5.2) to support language editing and improve clarity of presentation. All mathematical content, results, interpretations, and conclusions were developed by the author, who reviewed and edited the manuscript and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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